

APPLICATION OF REFRACTIVE INDEX IN THE STUDY OF CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION. PART II. DETERMINATION OF TRANSITION POINT OF CERTAIN HYDRATED INORGANIC SALTS IN SOLUTION BY REFRACTIVE INDEX

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Refractive index values of aqueous solutions of sodium sulphate and zinc sulphate between 20° and 50° show abrupt changes at certain temperatures. The values, so obtained, nearly agree with their transition points, determined by other methods.

Variations in the values of refractive index are usually uniform with rise of temperature. But it was observed by us earlier (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 149) that in the case of aqueous solutions of sodium carbonate and magnesium sulphate, there were abrupt changes at certain temperatures. These were found nearly the same as the transition points, determined by other methods. The work has now been extended to sodium sulphate and zinc sulphate, and in these cases also similar phenomenon has been noticed.

For these studies aqueous solutions of the salts of four different concentrations have been used. In the case of sodium sulphate, the concentrations of the solutions employed were $M/2$, $M/10$, $M/50$ and $M/250$ and the refractive index determinations were made between 20° and 50°. With all the four solutions, an irregularity in the uniform variation of refractive index was observed at 32.4°. This is in agreement with the values of previous workers by other methods: 32.6° (Dunstan and Langton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 418), 32.4° (Reichards and Wells, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 43, 471), 32.4° (Wuite, *ibid.*, 1914, 86, 349), 32.55° (Hartshorne, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2096). Another temperature of abrupt refractive index

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

variation has also been observed in case of all the solutions, but the value is not the same in all cases. This temperature was found to be 37.6° in case of the most concentrated solution ($M/2$) and 36.6° in the other three cases. [vide curve I(e), Fig. 2; II(e), III(e) and IV(e), Fig. 3]. This transition point has not been observed by previous workers, using other methods.

In the literature, another transition point (24.4° , White; *loc. cit.*; $23.465^\circ \pm .004$, Washburn and Clem, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 754) has been reported. This was not observed by us.

With four aqueous zinc sulphate solutions ($2.9899M$, $2.9899M/5$, $2.9899M/25$ and $2.9899M/125$), the abnormal changes in the variation of refractive index within 20° - 50° have been observed to take place in all cases only at 38° [vide curves-I(d), Fig. 1; II(d), Fig. 2; III(d), Fig. 3.] In the literature also within the range 20° - 50° , only one transition temperature appears to have been mentioned at 37.9° (Cohen and Hilterschij, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 118, 440, 443).

FIG. 3

EXPERIMENTAL

The crystalline sodium sulphate and zinc sulphate of A. R. quality (B.D.H.) and the same sample of conductivity water were used in all determinations. The experimental procedure adopted was the same as described before (*loc. cit.*).